

Synthesis, ion exchange properties, analytical and catalytic applications of nano sized cerium zirconium phosphate

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Manuscript received 02 February 2010, revised 09 June 2010, accepted 25 February 2011

Abstract : A novel inorganic cation exchange material, cerium zirconium phosphate (CZP) has been synthesized. Chemical composition of the compound was determined by ICP-AES method and structural studies were carried out using TGA, XRD and FTIR. From these, the formula of the exchanger is found to be $\text{CeO}_2 \cdot 2\text{ZrO}_2 \cdot 1.25\text{P}_2\text{O}_5 \cdot 14\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Properties like ion exchange capacity, pH titration, distribution coefficients for various metal ions, and the effect of ionic radii on ion exchange capacity have been studied. The results suggest that chemically resistive CZP is a promising inorganic cation exchanger in analytical and environmental chemistry. Distribution studies showed that the selectivity of the material towards various metal ions was in the order $\text{Pb}^{\text{II}} > \text{Cu}^{\text{II}} > \text{Zn}^{\text{II}} > \text{Mn}^{\text{II}} > \text{Cd}^{\text{II}} > \text{Y}^{\text{III}} > \text{Bi}^{\text{III}} > \text{Co}^{\text{II}} > \text{Ni}^{\text{II}} > \text{Ca}^{\text{II}} > \text{Al}^{\text{III}} > \text{Th}^{\text{IV}} > \text{Hg}^{\text{II}}$. Based on this, binary separation of Pb^{2+} and Cu^{2+} from Hg^{2+} and Th^{4+} were carried out on a column of the exchanger. The presence of protons contained in structural hydroxyl groups indicates good potential for application in solid acid catalysis and hydrolysis of sucrose was carried out for catalytic activity studies of the material.

Keywords : Ion exchanger, cerium zirconium phosphate, distribution coefficient, catalytic activity, binary separation.

Introduction

Inorganic ion exchangers are distinguished by their greater thermal stability at elevated temperatures, high chemical stability, resistance to high radiation fields, and their selectivity to certain ions which are the properties the organic resins tend to lack. Some of the inorganic ion exchangers have proved to have greater selectivity for trace radio nuclides compared to organic ion exchangers, and can be used over a wide pH range. Amongst the synthetic inorganic ion exchangers, tetravalent metal acid (TMA) salts¹⁻⁷ are gaining importance due to their excellent thermal stability and chemical resistivity. Although a lot of work has already been done on the synthesis of inorganic ion exchangers, the development of new inorganic ion exchangers with characteristic properties still needed attention and their utility in various fields is yet to be explored since the need for selective determination of heavy metal ions has increased immensely during last few decades due to growing environmental problems. TMA salts being synthesized by sol-gel routes, materials with varying water content, composition, ion exchange

capacity and crystallinity can be obtained by varying the parameters such as stoichiometry and concentration of the reagents used, temperature at which they are mixed, rate of addition, mode of mixing, and pH.

New mixed materials of this class with cation substitution are of interest since they show improved ion exchange properties and selectivity for particular metal ions in comparison to their single salt counter parts because cation substitution alters the properties, composition and dimensions of the structure. It has been reported that the affinity of antimony silicate towards cesium can be improved by doping with Ti^{4+} , Nb^{5+} , Mo^{6+} or W^{6+} in different mole ratios and it was found that cesium selectivity in acid was increased with a ternary Sb-Si-W system⁸. Preparation and characterization of sodium iron titanate ion exchanger⁹ and its application in heavy metal removal from waste waters has also been reported.

Zirconium-based ion exchangers have received attention because of their excellent ion-exchange behavior, stability and some important chemical applications in the field of ion exchange, ion-exchange membrane, and solid-

state electrochemistry. Synthesis of a mixed material of this class, zirconium titanium phosphate (ZTP)¹⁰ (tetravalent bimetallic acid salt – TBMA salt) by the sol-gel technique has been reported recently and various properties studied.

The objective of the present work is to explore the separation potential, analytical and catalytic application of cerium zirconium phosphate.

Experimental

Zirconyl chloride (Loba Chemie, India), ceric sulphate (E. Merck) and sodium dihydrogen phosphate (E. Merck) were used for the synthesis of the exchangers. All other reagents and chemicals used were of analytical grade.

Apparatus and instruments : A glass column was used for column operations. Elico LI613 pH meter was used for pH measurements and an electric thermostat oven was used for heating the samples at various temperatures. UV-Visible spectrophotometer model Jasco V660 was used for spectrophotometric measurements. FT-IR spectrometer model Thermo-Nicolet Avtar 370 for IR studies, X-ray diffractometer Bruker AXS D8 Advance for X-ray diffraction studies, Perkin-Elmer Diamond TG/DTA Analysis System for thermal analysis and an electric shaking machine for shaking were also used. Chemical composition was determined by ICP-AES method using ICP-AE spectrometer Thermo Electron IRIS Intrepid II.

Synthesis of the exchanger : Cerium zirconium phosphate (CZP) was synthesized by adding sodium dihydrogen phosphate solution to mixtures of zirconyl oxy chloride and ceric sulphate solutions with constant stirring, in different volume and mole ratios. The resulting gel was kept for 24 h at room temperature maintaining the pH at 1. It was then filtered, washed with deionized water and dried. The exchanger was then converted into the H⁺ form by immersing it in 1 M nitric acid for 24 h with occasional shaking and intermittent changing of acid. It was then washed with deionized water to remove the excess acid, dried and sieved to obtain particles of 60–100 mesh.

Ion exchange capacity (IEC) : The ion exchange capacity of the material was determined by column method. 1 g of the exchanger in H⁺ form was taken in a glass column of 1.1 cm diameter. The H⁺ ions were eluted by percolating 250 ml of 1 M sodium chloride solution. The effluent was collected and titrated against standard

sodium hydroxide solution. The exchange capacity (in meq/g) was calculated using the formula, av/w where a is the molarity, v is the volume of alkali used during titration and w is the weight of the exchanger taken.

Chemical stability : 0.5 g of exchanger was equilibrated with 50 ml of various solutions and kept overnight with occasional shaking. The amounts of zirconium, cerium and phosphate released in the acid solutions were determined spectrophotometrically.

Effect of temperature on IEC : The effect of temperature on ion exchange capacity was studied by heating several 1.0 g samples of the exchanger at different temperatures for three hours in an air oven and Na⁺ ion exchange capacity in meq g⁻¹ was determined by the column method after cooling them to room temperature.

pH titrations : Topp and Pepper method¹¹ was used for pH titrations using NaOH-NaCl, KOH-KCl, systems. 0.5 g of exchanger was equilibrated with varying amounts of metal chloride and metal hydroxide solutions. After equilibrium, the pH of the solutions was measured and plotted against the milliequivalents of OH⁻ added.

Distribution coefficient (K_d) : Distribution studies were carried out for various metal ions in demineralized water by batch process. In this method, 0.1 g of the exchanger (60–100 mesh) was equilibrated with 20 mL of the metal ion solutions for 24 h at room temperature. The metal ion concentrations before and after sorption were determined spectrophotometrically/by complexometric titration against standard EDTA solution. The K_d values were calculated using the formula,

$$K_d = \frac{(I - F)}{F} \times \frac{V}{W}$$

where, I is the initial volume of EDTA used, F the final volume of EDTA used, V is the volume of the metal ion solution (mL) and W is the weight of the exchanger.

Binary separation of metal ions : Separations of some metal ions of analytical utility were achieved on the column of cerium zirconium phosphate. The column on which the separations were to be carried out was filled uniformly with the exchanger. First of all distilled water was added to pack the granules so that no air bubbles get stuck. Then the mixture of the metal ion solutions was slowly poured. The process was repeated for maximum

sorption. The exchanged metal ions were eluted using suitable eluent.

Catalytic activity : Catalytic activity was studied by taking hydrolysis of sucrose as a model reaction. 20 ml sucrose solutions of various concentrations were treated

gravimetric analysis (Fig. 1) indicated about 30% weight loss up to about 120 °C due to the evaporation of water molecules. The number of water molecules in the material was determined on the basis of Alberti-Torraca¹² formula. From these, the proposed formula is CeO₂.2ZrO₂.

Table 1. Synthesis and properties of various samples of exchanger

Sample	Concentration (M)			Volume ratios	pH	Appearance	Ion exchange capacity for Na ⁺ (meq/g)
	Ce ⁴⁺	Zr ⁴⁺	PO ₄ ³⁻				
CZP 1	1	1	1	1 : 1 : 1	1	Yellow transparent	0.60
CZP 2	1	1	1	1 : 2 : 1	1	Yellow transparent	0.95
CZP 3	1	1	1	1 : 1 : 2	1	Yellow transparent	0.58
CZP 4	1	1	1	2 : 1 : 1	1	Yellow transparent	1.50
CZP 5	1	1	1	2 : 1 : 2	1	Yellow transparent	1.20
CZP 6	1	1	1	1 : 2 : 2	1	Yellow transparent	0.69

with the exchanger. The amount of reducing sugars formed was determined by using Benedict's quantitative reagent. This was repeated by varying the amount of exchanger, time and temperature.

Results and discussion

The exchanger, CZP4 obtained as yellow transparent amorphous solid having maximum ion exchange capacity 1.5 meq/g was selected for detailed study (Table 1). The material is found to be quite stable in lower concentrations of mineral acids such as HCl, H₂SO₄ and HNO₃ (Table 2).

Elemental analysis by ICP-AES revealed a cerium, zirconium, phosphorous ratio of 1 : 2 : 2.5. Thermo

Table 2. Chemical stability of cerium zirconium phosphate CZP in different solvents

Solution	Ce ^{IV} released	Zr ^{IV} released	PO ₄ ³⁻ released
H ₂ O	0.00	0.00	0.00
0.1 M HNO ₃	0.00	0.00	0.00
0.5 M HNO ₃	0.00	0.00	0.00
1.0 M HNO ₃	0.00	0.00	0.00
2.0 M HNO ₃	0.02	0.00	0.18
0.1 M HCl	0.00	0.00	0.00
0.5 M HCl	0.00	0.00	0.00
1.0 M HCl	0.21	0.00	1.65
0.1 M H ₂ SO ₄	0.00	0.00	0.00
0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	0.26	0.00	0.21
0.1 M NaOH	0.62	0.48	1.95
0.5 M NaOH	3.00	4.87	4.87

Fig. 1. TG of CZP.

$1.25\text{P}_2\text{O}_5 \cdot 14\text{H}_2\text{O}$. At about $350\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ phosphate get converted to pyrophosphate.

FTIR spectra of CZP (Fig. 2) showed a broad band in the region $\sim 3433\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which is attributed to symmetric and asymmetric -OH stretching, while the band at $\sim 1632\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is attributed to H-O-H bending. A band in the region $\sim 1051\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is attributed to P=O stretching and a

band at $\sim 1384\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is attributed to the presence of δ (POH). This indicates the presence of structural hydroxyl protons in CZP, which is more evident from the obtained IEC values. Bands at ~ 604 and ~ 521 shows the presence of Zr-O and Ce-O bonds.

XRD analysis (Fig. 3) showed amorphous nature of the exchanger and the average diameter of particle was

Fig. 2. FTIR of CZP.

Fig. 3. XRD of CZP.

found to be 20.4 nm which is in the nano range. The particle size was calculated from the full width at half-maximum of the peak using Debye-Scherrer equation¹³, $D = 0.9 \lambda / \beta_{2\theta} \cdot \cos \theta_{\max}$, where D is the average crystal size in nm, λ is the characteristic wavelength of X-ray used, θ is the diffraction angle and $\beta_{2\theta}$ is the angular width in radians at an intensity equal to half of the maximum peak intensity.

pH titration curve showed monofunctional nature of the exchanger (Fig. 4). The exchange capacity obtained from the curve is in agreement with that obtained by the column method.

Fig. 4. pH titration curve of CZP.

The effect of size and charge on ion exchange capacity was studied for alkali metals and the order was found to be $\text{Na}^+ < \text{K}^+$; $\text{Mg}^{2+} < \text{Ba}^{2+}$ (Table 3). The sodium ion exchange capacity decreases (Table 3) slightly with temperature and the sample retained prominent capacity up to 100 °C.

Table 3

Effect of hydrated ionic radii and charge on IEC			Effect of temperature on IEC		
Metal ion	Hydrated ionic radii	IEC (meq/g)	Temp. (°C)	Duration (h)	Na ⁺ IEC
Na ⁺	7.90	1.5	50	3	1.20
K ⁺	5.30	1.7	100	3	0.82
Mg ²⁺	10.80	1.8	200	3	0.54
Ba ²⁺	8.80	1.9	300	3	0.25

The distribution studies of metal ions (Tables 4 and 5) showed that the exchanger has very high affinity towards Pb²⁺ ion in comparison to other metal ions studied. The selectivity was found to be in the order : $\text{Pb}^{\text{II}} > \text{Cu}^{\text{II}} >$

Table 4. K_d values of various metal ions in water

Ions	Taken as	K_d
Pb ²⁺	Nitrate	1228
Zn ²⁺	Sulphate	192.6
Mn ²⁺	Sulphate	170.5
Ni ²⁺	Chloride	95.6
Hg ²⁺	Chloride	NE
Ca ²⁺	Chloride	78.1
Cd ²⁺	Chloride	144.5
Co ²⁺	Chloride	106.7
Cu ²⁺	Sulphate	683.0
Al ³⁺	Sulphate	74.5
Bi ³⁺	Nitrate	115.8
Y ³⁺	Nitrate	126.0
Th ⁴⁺	Nitrate	NE

NE - Negligible exchange.

$\text{Zn}^{\text{II}} > \text{Mn}^{\text{II}} > \text{Cd}^{\text{II}} > \text{Y}^{\text{III}} > \text{Bi}^{\text{III}} > \text{Co}^{\text{II}} > \text{Ni}^{\text{II}} > \text{Ca}^{\text{II}} > \text{Al}^{\text{III}} > \text{Th}^{\text{IV}} > \text{Hg}^{\text{II}}$.

Its high selectivity for lead ions enabled it to act as an efficient ion exchanger for the separation of Pb^{II} and Cu^{II} from Hg^{II}, Th^{IV} and Al^{III}. For this, effect of electrolyte concentrations on K_d values (Table 4) were studied and some binary separations (Table 6) were carried out using the exchanger.

Catalytic studies : For catalytic studies, hydrolysis of sucrose was carried out using the exchanger. The results of hydrolysis are summarized in Table 7. The influence of various reaction parameters, such as, catalyst loading and initial concentration of sucrose on the hydrolysis; was studied. With increase in catalyst amount and concentration of reactant the yield increases. From the table it is found that with 1 g of catalyst loading and with 20 ml of 0.5 M sucrose solution at 50 °C, 99% conversion could be achieved within two hours. The catalyst was recycled and reused with negligible loss in the activity.

Conclusion :

The increasing presence of toxic pollutants in the environment is perceived as a major problem in this century. Since lead is a cumulative poison, even at trace levels it poses long-term health risks, especially for young children. So regulation of lead contamination in the environment, and water resources in particular, requires the development of various methods for the removal of it and cerium zirconium phosphate is found to exhibit the charac-

Table 5. Effect of electrolyte concentration on distribution coefficients of metal ions

Cation	Taken as	DMW	K_d values					
			HNO ₃			NH ₄ NO ₃		
			0.1 M	0.01 M	0.001 M	0.1 M	0.01 M	0.001 M
Pb ^{II}	NO ₃ ⁻	1228	548	750	987	527	703	964
Cu ^{II}	SO ₄ ²⁻	683	386	498	554	344	402	520
Hg ^{II}	Cl ⁻	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE
Th ^{IV}	NO ₃ ⁻	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE
Al ^{III}	NO ₃ ⁻	74.5	NE	25	56	5	23	67

NE - Negligible exchange

Table 6. Binary separation of metal ions on cerium zirconium phosphate

Separations achieved	Eluent	Metal ion (mg)		% Efficiency
		Loaded	Eluted	
Pb ^{II}	1 M HNO ₃ + 0.2 M NH ₄ NO ₃	2.35	2.30	97.8
Hg ^{II}	DMW	3.00	2.94	98.0
Pb ^{II}	1 M HNO ₃ + 0.2 M NH ₄ NO ₃	2.35	2.32	98.7
Th ^{IV}	DMW	3.50	3.42	97.7
Cu ^{II}	0.5 M HNO ₃ + 1 M NH ₄ NO ₃	2.50	2.44	97.6
Hg ^{II}	DMW	3.00	2.97	99.0
Cu ^{II}	0.5 M HNO ₃ + 1 M NH ₄ NO ₃	2.50	2.47	98.8
Th ^{IV}	DMW	3.00	2.92	97.3
Cu ^{II}	0.5 M HNO ₃ + 1 M NH ₄ NO ₃	2.50	2.46	98.4
Al ^{III}	0.1 M HNO ₃	2.53	2.50	98.2
Pb ^{II}	1 M HNO ₃ + 0.2 M NH ₄ NO ₃	2.35	2.31	98.3
Al ^{III}	0.1 M HNO ₃	2.53	2.52	99.6

Table 7. Catalytic activity of CZP - Effect of concentration and catalyst loading on hydrolysis of sucrose at 50 °C

Conc of sucrose solution	Volume taken (ml)	Weight of exchanger (g)	Time (h)	Percentage conversion
0.05 M	20	1	1	52
0.05 M	20	2	1	61
0.10 M	20	1	1	69
0.10 M	20	2	1	85
0.25 M	20	1	2	99
0.50 M	20	1	2	99

teristics of a promising inorganic cation exchanger for the removal of lead. The exchanger can also be used as a solid acid catalyst in place of liquid corrosive acid cata-

lyst in the inversion of cane sugar. This exchanger can be used as a multipurpose solid exchanger because of its nano size.

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